

Guidelines to enable interoperability of in-situ networks and connection with GEOSS

Project Identification

Project Full Title	Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation
Project Acronym	Water-ForCE
Grant Agreement	101004186
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months

Document Identification

Deliverable number	D4.6
Deliverable Title	Guidelines to enable interoperability of in-situ networks and connection with GEOSS
Type of Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Work Package	WP4
Leading Partner	NIRDBS

History of Changes

Date	Version	Comments
15.11.2022	V0	Preliminary report
07.12.2022	V1	First draft
12.12.2022	v1.1	Second draft
24.01.2023	v1.2	Third draft
29.01.2023	V1.3	Forth draft (first candidate for final version)
06.04.2023	V1.4	Intermediary version
15.04.2023	V1.5	Final version (changes made according to the comments of the reviewer)

List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content Management System
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EO	Earth Observation
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
JS	JavaScript
TRD	Trustworthy Digital Repositories
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Working Package

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	5
2. Data Interoperability	7
3. FAIR Principles	9
3.1 Findable	9
F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	9
F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	9
F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe	9
F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	10
3.2 Accessible	10
A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	10
A2: Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available	10
3.3 Interoperable	10
I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	11
I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles	11
I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	11
3.4 Reusable	11
R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	11
R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	11
R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	12
R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	12
4. TRUST principles	12
4.1 Transparency	12
4.2 Responsibility	12
4.3 User Focus	12
4.4 Sustainability	13
4.5 Technology	13
5. FAIRness of Copernicus	13
5.1 FAIRness automated tools	14
FAIR-Checker	15
FAIR-Enough	16
F-UJI	18
5.2 FAIRness aggregator utility	20
5.3 Copernicus data hubs assessment	22
Technical analysis of the front-end	22

Technical analysis of the back-end/databases	26
5.4 FAIR technical implementation discussion	27
Metadata embedding / serving	27
Schemas / Vocab / Ontologies	28
6. Domain specific mapping	28
7. References	36
8. Annex	37

Executive Summary

- The current deliverable evaluates the Status Quo of the currently used databases to give guidelines to enable interoperability of databases (with accent for in-situ ones) and connections with GEOSS
- We investigated all the Copernicus Services (Atmosphere, Marine, Land, Climate Change, Security, Emergency) for FAIRness classification to give suggestions and improve their usage through interoperability and adoption
- Each Copernicus Service uses a different platform, and has various FAIRness scores. The Marine one has the biggest score of 1.74/4, while Land has 0.57/4. Compared to a score of 3.51/4 of the PANGAEA platform the comparison was made against.
- The analysed Marine Service partially has the required information available as text in the served webpage. It needs to be properly mapped to the correct meta tags in order for it to be FAIR compliant and machine-readable.
- In order to be in the spirit of the FAIR guidelines, a proper standardised vocabulary must be implemented in the meta tags, in order for raise the Interoperability score.
- Since Copernicus uses different web portals for their Services, with each of them being FAIR at various levels, they should adopt a standard web platform for all their hubs, on which to work to meet the FAIR guidelines. Working separately on several different versions of their Services is not effective, nor efficient.

1. Introduction

The idea of the deliverable was to focus on the known platforms and give guidelines to better integrate the obtained data of Copernicus with the in-situ data. To achieve this objective the initial plan was to focus on the GEOSS platform (<https://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>) that was a very promising candidate for integrating the data. Unfortunately the GEOSS system seems not to have been updated in the recent years: the above link provides the list of the data providers as of March 2017 for example or in the documents section the Manual for becoming a GEO Data Provider https://www.earthobservations.org/documents/gci/201711_gci_manual_01.pdf the current version of the manual is from November 2017.

Furthermore, if one runs statistics on the GEOSS portal based on the user's countries for Site Usage (interval 1 January 2022-31 December 2022) we would get the following chart:

Analyzed period: 2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31

Created on 2023-01-29 12:52

GEOSS version: 3.6.9.8

The chart shows the top 20 countries of origin for usage of the GEOSS platform. Data obtained by geo-locating based on IP address of the user with the top 3 users being the US (4335), Kosovo (3435) and China (2892), the EU countries coming on the positions 4 (Italy with 1723 users), 5 (Germany with 1428 users), 7 (France with 981 users), 8 (Spain with 873 users) and 10 (Netherlands 779 users).

Analysing one month of GEOSS usages (we chose November 2022 so that it does not have holidays that could disrupt the statistics) we obtain a similar statistic (for clarity we chose to have the chart for the top 10 countries):

Analyzed period: 2022-11-01 - 2022-11-30

Created on 2023-01-29 13:09

GEOSS version: 3.6.9.8

We have roughly the same results as before with the EU member states on positions 4,6,7,10 with the number of users per month 160, 133, 86, 69 respectively.

At the moment all data from the Copernicus Services can be accessed also from the GEOSS portal, thus the interoperability component with the in-situ data depends on the non-Copernicus data.

Considering all these and other discussions in the WP4 related to GEOSS and its maintaining plus the opportunities for improvement we decided to focus more at the FAIR principles [Wilkinson 2016] and their adoption for the Copernicus Services as this will have a bigger impact on the usage and data adoption and interoperability.

2. Data Interoperability

Data interoperability is the ability of different systems and applications to exchange and use data with each other. It is a critical aspect of the FAIR principles because it allows data to be used across different systems and applications, which can help to accelerate scientific discovery. Data interoperability is achieved by using open, non-proprietary data formats, providing clear documentation of data structures and relationships, and making data available through open, well-documented APIs.

One of the main challenges of data interoperability is dealing with data that is stored in different formats. Different systems and applications often use different data formats, which can make it difficult for them to exchange and use data with each other. To address this challenge, it is important to use open, non-proprietary data formats that can be easily used by different systems and applications. This can include formats like CSV, JSON, and XML, which are widely supported and can be easily used by different systems and applications.

We now give the following list of guidelines for data interoperability that was discussed and refined in the WP4. We consider these guidelines both important and non-exhaustive but also covered on various degrees by the FAIR and TRUST principles (described in the next sections):

Guidelines for interoperability of data:

Use open, non-proprietary data formats: Data should be made available in formats that are widely supported and can be easily used by different systems and applications. This can include formats like CSV, JSON, and XML.

Provide detailed metadata and documentation: Detailed metadata and documentation are essential for understanding the content and context of the data, which helps to ensure that it can be easily used and integrated with other data.

Use standard protocols and web services: Standard protocols and web services, such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Web Coverage Service (WCS) and Web Feature Service (WFS) standards, can help to ensure that data can be easily integrated with other systems and applications.

Use standard vocabularies: Use standard vocabularies, such as the ISO 19115 standard for metadata, to ensure that data is described in a consistent and standardized way that can be easily understood by different systems and applications.

Provide data through open, well-documented APIs: Data should be made available through open, well-documented APIs, which allows others to easily access and use the data in their own applications.

Ensure data is discoverable: Data should be easily discoverable, which can be achieved through the use of persistent identifiers, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), and the provision of detailed metadata.

Provide clear licensing information: Clear licensing information is important because it allows others to understand the terms and conditions of using the data.

Make data available in multiple formats: Making data available in multiple formats allows others to use the data in the format that best suits their needs.

Provide mechanisms for authentication and authorization if necessary: Authentication and authorization mechanisms can be used to ensure that only authorized individuals can access the data.

Adopt the Copernicus Data and Information Access Service (DIAS) as a key data hub for in-situ data, to ensure that the data is easily discoverable, accessible, and usable for a wide range of users.

Use of globally recognized and established data standards, such as Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) standards, to ensure the data is easily understood by other systems and applications.

Use of common data models for the in-situ data to ensure that the data can be easily integrated with other data.

Regularly update and maintain the data, to ensure that it remains accurate and up-to-date.

Ensure that data is available in a machine-readable format, which makes it easier for other systems and applications to use the data.

Use of web services and APIs to provide access to the data, which makes it easy for others to use and integrate with other systems and applications.

Use of clear and consistent naming conventions for the data, to make it easy for others to understand the data.

Use of a common spatial reference system, such as WGS 84, to ensure that the data can be easily integrated with other data.

Use of a common temporal reference system, such as UTC, to ensure that the data can be easily integrated with other data.

Provide the data in a format that is easy to use and understand, such as a CSV or JSON file.

We now pass to the FAIR principles and their detailed description with a focus on Interoperability of data.

3. FAIR Principles

In essence, the FAIR principles are guidelines for data management practices to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

FAIR applies to both the data(set) and the metadata describing the data(set).

As the FAIR principles are merely guidelines, and not a standard or hard rule, the implementation/FAIRification of data has a lot of wiggle room stemming from the interpretation of the guidelines, this issue is further compounded by the differences between different research domains.

3.1 Findable

The first principle, Findable, refers to the ability of others to locate and identify data. This includes providing detailed metadata and using persistent identifiers, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), to ensure data can be easily discovered. Metadata is information that describes the data, such as its title, author, date of creation, and keywords that describe the content. By providing detailed metadata, others can quickly understand the content and context of the data, which makes it more discoverable. Persistent identifiers, such as DOIs, ensure that data can be easily found and accessed, even if the location of the data changes.

The (meta)data must be easily findable by humans and machines, especially for facilitating automatic discovery of said data. The Findable principle has 4 specific sub principles.

F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

This means that each dataset must be findable at a specific URL, with a specific persistent ID. Example: [doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)

F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

Datasets must be accompanied by extensive metadata fields that describe the data as much as possible, in order to make it easier for both man and machine to understand it.

F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

The data and metadata can be separate files/URI, thus it is important that the metadata file/URI explicitly references the data file/URI, by the unique ID mentioned at F1.

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

In essence, scientific datasets are not always easily findable, as the web crawler (a ‘robot’ used by search engines to find resources on the web) might just not find the data, thus the data owner should manually index their data on relevant data repositories or search engines.

A limitation of this principle is that it assumes that the data is already well-organized and catalogued, when, in practice, many datasets are not well-organized, and it can be difficult to locate the data that is needed. Organizing the data requires additional resources.

3.2 Accessible

The second principle, Accessible, refers to the ability of others to access and use data. This includes providing clear licensing information and making data available in multiple formats, as well as providing mechanisms for authentication and authorization if necessary. Clear licensing information is important because it allows others to understand the terms and conditions of using the data. By making data available in multiple formats, others can use the data in the format that best suits their needs. Authentication and authorization mechanisms are used to ensure that only authorized individuals can access the data.

The data must be stored long-term, and it must describe how it can be accessed/used by the interested parties. Example: *Author permission required, contact at john@doe.io*

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol

Data must be accessible easily, assuming credentials / usage rights are provided, without the need of specialised/proprietary tools, or requiring non-standard communication protocols.

For all intents and purposes, this just means the data has to be accessible via ftp/http and other web browser compatible protocols.

A2: Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available

Because storing actual datasets long-term is expensive, both economically and computationally, overtime the datasets will no longer be available.

However, as metadata files are by default extremely small compared to the actual dataset, the expectation is that these should be stored and made available for more time than the actual dataset. This assumes the metadata is rich as described by F2.

One limitation of this principle is that the data is assumed to be easily read and understood, which can be problematic if the data is too complex to be described in the required manner.

3.3 Interoperable

The third principle, Interoperable, refers to the ability of data to be used with other data and tools. This includes using open, non-proprietary data formats and providing clear

documentation of data structures and relationships. Interoperability is important because it allows data to be used in different systems and applications, which can help to accelerate scientific discovery. Open, non-proprietary data formats are important because they can be easily used by others, regardless of the software or hardware that they use. Clear documentation of data structures and relationships is important because it allows others to understand the data and how it relates to other data.

Data should be available in a standard format that can be accessed by common tools (ex: csv), as opposed to proprietary formats.

I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

In the case of scientific data, the (meta)data must use controlled vocabularies or ontologies, so the machine/human reading the data has the guarantee that “apples” are actually apples, and not oranges.

I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles

The control vocabularies should be documented and available through unique and persistent IDs. Example: BioPortal Ontology Service.

I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

The (meta)data should be explicit if it uses other (meta)data sets or if it is split across different sets.

A limitation of this principle is that it assumes that data is already well-structured in a format that can be easily integrated. Many datasets are not inherently that way and may not be easily integrated with other data sources. Another assumption is that the data can be easily mapped to a common format or model, which will likely not be the case in some situations.

3.4 Reusable

The fourth principle, Reusable, refers to the ability of data to be used for multiple purposes. This includes providing detailed metadata and provenance information, as well as making data available through open, well-documented APIs. Provenance information is important because it allows others to understand the history of the data, including how it was created, who created it, and any modifications that have been made. By making data available through open, well-documented APIs, others can easily access and use the data in their own applications.

R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

Data must be (re)usable, thus it needs to be described properly and relevantly for the dataset/research domain.

R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

Data must contain the license used, and has to be machine-readable.

R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

Data must contain author information, and how the data was obtained.

R1.3: (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

4. TRUST principles

While the FAIR principles tackle good practices for actual data objects, TRUST principles tackle the issue of sustainably storing and curating the data long-term through trustworthy digital depositories (TRD) (Lin et al., 2020). The acronym TRUST stands for Transparency, Reproducibility, Usability, and Traceability.

4.1 Transparency

To be transparent about specific repository services and data holdings that are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence.

- Terms of use, both for the repository and for the data holdings.
- Minimum digital preservation timeframe for the data holdings.
- Any pertinent additional features or services, for example the capacity to responsibly steward sensitive data.

4.2 Responsibility

To be responsible for ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data holdings and for the reliability and persistence of its service.

- Adhering to the designated community's metadata and curation standards, along with providing stewardship of the data holdings e.g. technical validation, documentation, quality control, authenticity protection, and long-term persistence.
- Providing data services e.g. portal and machine interfaces, data download or server-side processing.
- Managing the intellectual property rights of data producers, the protection of sensitive information resources, and the security of the system and its content.

4.3 User Focus

To ensure that the data management norms and expectations of target user communities are met.

- Implementing relevant data metrics and making these available to users.

- Providing (or contributing to) community catalogues to facilitate data discovery.
- Monitoring and identifying evolving community expectations and responding as required to meet these changing needs.

4.4 Sustainability

To sustain services and preserve data holdings for the long-term.

- Planning sufficiently for risk mitigation, business continuity, disaster recovery, and succession.
- Securing funding to enable ongoing usage and to maintain the desirable properties of the data resources that the repository has been entrusted with preserving and disseminating.
- Providing governance for necessary long-term preservation of data so that data resources remain discoverable, accessible, and usable in the future.

4.5 Technology

To provide infrastructure and capabilities to support secure, persistent, and reliable services.

- Implementing relevant and appropriate standards, tools, and technologies for data management and curation.
- Having plans and mechanisms in place to prevent, detect, and respond to cyber or physical security threats.

In essence, the TRUST principles in scientific data management aim to ensure the quality, integrity, and trustworthiness of scientific data by promoting transparency, reproducibility, usability, and traceability. Through the implementation of these principles, scientific data can be made more reliable and trustworthy, which can lead to more efficient and impactful research.

5. FAIRness of Copernicus

Copernicus.eu is split into 6 services, or data stores. Each data store uses a different platform/content management system. Thus, each of them has to be assessed individually as they are different from one another to various degrees.

Below is the infrastructure of Copernicus' Climate Data Storage (Copernicus Climate, 2021).

Users, data suppliers, as well as API consumers, interact directly with the Web Portal component, which in turn gets its data from the Back End component. Thus, any metadata present or missing that would satisfy FAIR sub principles has to be served by the back-end, and displayed on the front-end (web portal) for any consumer to see/read.

5.1 FAIRness automated tools

We have identified 3 automated tools that allow the assessment of resources:

1. **FAIR-Checker:** <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/check>
2. **FAIR-Enough:** <https://fair-enough.semanticscience.org/>
3. **F-UJI:** <https://www.f-uji.net/index.php>

All the tools work based on the principle of querying the html of the web page containing the dataset. What is different between them is how they extract/infer what the metadata is, and how they interpret it relative to the FAIR principles.

For example, resource <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331>, when analysed through each of the tools, has the following scores:

FAIR-Checker

This tool is developed by a working group of the French Institute for Bioinformatics ([details here](#)). The source code is made available on their GitHub [page](#). Specific details on how they have implemented the sub principle assessments can be inferred from the individual metrics source, found [here](https://github.com/IFB-ElixirFr/FAIR-checker/tree/master/metrics): <https://github.com/IFB-ElixirFr/FAIR-checker/tree/master/metrics>.

Check

How FAIR is my resource ?

Enter resource identifier (URL/DOI)

[https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331](#)

Test all metrics

The URL/DOI is valid - The input contains the following DOIs that you can also test: [10.1594/PANGAEA.914331](#)

Clean results

Dataset Dataserve Workflow Publication Datasite Dataset Tool

Radar chart of metrics completion

List of metrics with details and results Export

Principle	Name	Description	Comment	Recommendation	Score	Result	Test	Details
F1A	Unique IDs				2	Success	Check	
F1B	Persistent IDs				2	Success	Check	
F2A	Structured metadata				2	Success	Check	
F2B	Shared vocabularies for metadata			You should express all your metadata with properties Read more	1	Success	Check	
A1.1	Open resolution protocol				2	Success	Check	
I1	Machine readable format				2	Success	Check	
I2	Use shared ontologies			You should express all your metadata with properties Read more	1	Success	Check	
I3	External links				2	Success	Check	
R1.1	Metadata includes license				2	Success	Check	
R1.2	Metadata includes provenance			You should include information about provenance in your Read more	0	Failure	Check	
R1.3	Community standards			You should express all your metadata with properties Read more	1	Success	Check	

For additional tips and recommendations on how to improve your resource, we recommend you to use the FAIR Cookbook:
<https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/home.html>

The analysed resource fails the sub principle R1.2 test of the FAIR-Checker tool, resulting in a percentage score of 66.7% for the Reusable principle.

FAIR-Enough

This tool is developed by Maastricht University ([details](#)), the source code is available [here](#). The assessment selection allows the user to select specific collections of tests. One collection is implemented based on the [FAIRMetrics working group](#), started/maintained by Mark Wilkinson, the main author of the “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship” paper, another uses a combination between FAIRMetrics and metrics interpreted by the tool developer. This tool is the first to allow the assessment of community specific tailored metrics, through the [Rare Disease FAIR](#) implementation.

Collection Metrics Tests

RESTful API GraphQL API

<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331>

Identifier of this evaluation: <https://w3id.org/fair-enough/evaluations/3a905ef0eed4c8fa6329b3921318f793a8d87179>

Evaluated in 4s with the fair-enough-metadata collection on the 2022-11-13

Extracted metadata
© License: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Evaluation score: 12/16

75%

Log level: Success, warnings and failures

Findable

- F1 - Resource identifier is persistent**

<https://w3id.org/fair-enough/metrics/tests/f1-metadata-identifier-persistent> - Version: d.1.0 - Metric to test if the unique identifier of the metadata resource is likely to be persistent. We test known URL persistence schemas (purl, doi, w3id, identifiers.org).

Test result URL: <https://w3id.org/fair-enough/metrics/metrics/f1-metadata-identifier-persistent#https%3A%2F%2Fdoi.pangaea.de%2F10.1594%2FPANGAEA.914331/result-2022-06-29T12:33:59+01:00>

FAILURE: [2022-11-13T14:05:48] The given resource URI <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331> is not considered a persistent URI.
- F1 - Resource metadata identifier is unique**
- F3 - Metadata is organized and machine-readable**

The screenshot displays the FAIR-Enough tool interface, which is organized into four main sections, each with a distinct background color and a search icon:

- Findable (Light Blue):** Contains six metrics:
 - F1 - Resource identifier is persistent (Fail)
 - F1 - Resource metadata identifier is unique (Pass)
 - F2 - Metadata is grounded and machine-readable (Pass)
 - F2 - Metadata is structured (Pass)
 - F3 - Metadata identifier explicitly in metadata (Fail)
 - F4 - The resource is indexed in a searchable resource (Fail)
- Accessible (Light Orange):** Contains three metrics:
 - A1.1 - Metadata uses an open free protocol for metadata retrieval (Pass)
 - A1.2 - Metadata authentication and authorization (Pass)
 - A2 - Metadata is persistent (Fail)
- Interoperable (Light Green):** Contains five metrics:
 - I1 - Metadata uses a formal semantic knowledge representation language (Pass)
 - I1 - Metadata uses a formal structured knowledge representation language (Pass)
 - I2 - Metadata uses FAIR Vocabularies registered in known repositories (Pass)
 - I2 - Metadata uses resolvable FAIR Vocabularies (Pass)
 - I3 - Metadata contains outward references (Pass)
- Reusable (Light Purple):** Contains two metrics:
 - R1 - Metadata includes a License (Pass)
 - R1 - Metadata includes a standard License (Pass)

The same resource, tested in FAIR-Enough, fails part of the Findable and Accessible principles, which it didn't in the previous tool.

F-UJI

Developed by a working group from University of Bremen ([details](#)), which also manages the PANGAEA repository, this tool ([source code](#)) is the first to implement FAIRsFAIR core metrics (Devaraju et al., 2022) to evaluate the FAIRness of a resource.

FAIRsFAIR metrics are based on the work of RDA in which the general FAIR guidelines have been defined in a more concrete and actionable form (FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, 2020).

F-UJI Home Assess About Methods Docs Code

FAIR assessment

Disclaimer:
The test results shown here are based on preliminary data and code which still is under development. F-UJI is rapidly evolving and not yet available in a productive environment.

[Click here to assess another data set](#)

Assessment Results:

Evaluated Resource:

Abundance and biomass of Calanus spp. and near surface and bottom temperature and salinity on western North Atlantic Shelves

[View](#) [JSON](#) [New](#)

FAIR level: advanced

Resource PID(URL): <https://doi.org/10.1024/FANGAEA.014331>

DataCite support: enabled

Metric Version: metrics_v0.5

Metric Specification: <https://doi.org/10.32811/zenodo.4081213>

Software version: 2.2.1

Download assessment results: [JSON](#)

Save and share assessment results:

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	3 of 3	advanced
Interoperable:	4 of 4	advanced
Reusable:	7 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable	
Fsf-F1-010 - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✓
Fsf-F1-020 - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✓
Fsf-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✓
Fsf-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✓
Fsf-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved programmatically.	✓
Accessible	
Fsf-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	✓
Fsf-A1-02D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	✓
Fsf-A1-02M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	✓
Interoperable	
Fsf-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	✓
Fsf-I2-01M - Metadata uses semantic resources	✓
Fsf-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	✓
Reusable	
Fsf-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.	✓
Fsf-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	✓
Fsf-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	✓
Fsf-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.	✓
Fsf-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.	✓

In the F-UJI tool, the analysed resource reports issues with a sub principle from Reusable, like it did in the FAIR-Checker tool. The difference being that in F-UJI, it only soft-fails the test, as it detected partial compliance with the sub principle.

5.2 FAIRness aggregator utility

As stated before, FAIR principles are only broad/abstract guidelines which do not point to concrete solutions/implementations, thus there is a lot of wiggle room in how the sub principles are interpreted and assessed, making it is possible for one dataset to fail a test from one of tool and pass in another, as shown previously.

For this reason, we've made a utility that will automatically assess resources in each of the before mentioned tools, and output a report of the averaged scores. It can be found here: <https://github.com/NIRDBS/FAIRxCheck>

The utility is written in python, with the current alpha version running locally. In essence, it acts as a wrapper for the selenium automation framework, and it works like this:

1. the user feeds it a list of web URLs

2. the utility iterates through the list doing the following:
 1. opens tool 1 (ex: Fair-Checker), puts the URL in the tool to analyse.
 2. stores the results reported by tool 1.
 3. repeat with the rest of the tools.
3. after iterating through the list, it will then output an aggregated report with FAIR scores for each URL, and a granular report which shows the scores of each tool used, for each URL.

Examples below:

```

→ python3 fairxcheck.py resources.csv
[ ASSESSING RESOURCE 1/1 ]
URL: https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331
FAIR-Checker: Finished!
F-UJI: Finished!
FAIR-Enough: Finished!

[ DONE ] Report name: 07-12-2022 1922.csv
    
```

aggr_07-10-2022 2132

resource	F	A	I	R	FAIR_score	datetime
https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331	0.83	0.89	1.0	0.79	3.51	2022-10-07 21:25:34.700569
https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.15454/PIMPHZ	0.65	0.89	0.39	0.18	2.11	2022-10-07 21:26:42.312109
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004/INFORMATION	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0.57	2022-10-07 21:27:29.621618
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/OCEANCOLOUR_BLK_BGC_L3_MY_009_153/INFOR	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0.57	2022-10-07 21:28:15.265089
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/SEALEVEL_EUR_PHY_L3_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_008	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0.57	2022-10-07 21:28:59.844324
https://land.copernicus.vgt.vito.be/PDF/portal/Application.html#Browse	0.48	1.0	0.31	0.14	1.93	2022-10-07 21:29:25.867987
https://land.copernicus.vgt.vito.be/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/urn:cglis:global:wl_v2_la	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0.57	2022-10-07 21:30:23.064247
https://land.copernicus.vgt.vito.be/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/urn:cglis:global:lswt_v1	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0.57	2022-10-07 21:31:18.177089
https://land.copernicus.vgt.vito.be/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/urn:cglis:continents:lie_v	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0	2022-10-07 21:32:13.018233
https://data.eumetsat.int/product/EO:EUM:DAT:METOP:AMSUL1	0.49	0.33	0.33	0.22	1.37	2022-10-07 21:32:38.797964

06-10-2022 1324

resource	tool	F	A	I	R	report_url	datetime	status
https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331	FAIR-Checker	4/4	1/1	3/3	2/3		2022-10-06 13:03:23.542048	success
https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331	F-UJI	7/7	3/3	4/4	7/10		2022-10-06 13:03:36.344007	success
https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331	FAIR-Enough	0/6	3/3	2/5	5/2	https://fair-enough.se	2022-10-06 13:03:46.710150	success
https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.15454/PIMPHZ	FAIR-Checker	3/4	1/1	2/3	1/3		2022-10-06 13:03:56.728732	success
https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.15454/PIMPHZ	F-UJI	6/7	1/3	1/4	2/10		2022-10-06 13:04:29.481710	success
https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.15454/PIMPHZ	FAIR-Enough	3/6	2/3	4/5	0/2	https://fair-enough.se	2022-10-06 13:04:42.192507	success
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004/INFORMATION	FAIR-Checker	1/4	1/1	0/3	0/3		2022-10-06 13:04:57.233373	success
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004/INFORMATION	F-UJI	1/7	0/3	0/4	0/10		2022-10-06 13:05:29.102316	success
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004/INFORMATION	FAIR-Enough	1/6	2/3	0/5	0/2	https://fair-enough.se	2022-10-06 13:05:35.172978	success
https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/OCEANCOLOUR_BLK_BGC_L3_MY_009_153/INFOR	FAIR-Checker	1/4	1/1	0/3	0/3		2022-10-06 13:05:42.702501	success

Note: the utility can only assess publicly available resources, if a resource is behind a login wall, it cannot be automatically assessed. The utility can also not assess resources that have no unique identifier (or those not machine readable due to technical reasons).

5.3 Copernicus data hubs assessment

The utility was used to assess the following Copernicus resources, alongside a PANGAEA resource used as an example of a high-scoring FAIR resource:

1. https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004/description
2. <https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts?tab=overview>
3. <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cems-glofas-seasonal-reforecast?tab=overview>
4. https://land.copernicus.vgt.vito.be/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/urn:cgl:global:w1_v2_lakes
5. <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331>

The aggregated report is show below:

resource	F	A	I	R	FAIR_score	datetime
https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004/de	0.48	0.89	0.22	0.14	1.73	2022-11-13 18:54:47.422311
https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-europe-air-quality-f	0.41	0.33	0.33	0.22	1.29	2022-11-13 18:55:15.918956
https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cems-glofas-seasonal-reforec	0.41	0.33	0.33	0.22	1.29	2022-11-13 18:55:42.499149
https://land.copernicus.vgt.vito.be/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/	0.24	0.33	0.0	0.0	0.57	2022-11-13 18:56:41.135534
https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331	0.83	0.89	1.0	0.79	3.51	2022-11-13 18:57:34.880361

As we can see, the highest scoring Copernicus resource is the marine one, with a total score of 1.73. The Atmosphere and Climate hubs have the same score because they use the same CMS, while the Land one has the lowest score. The PANGAEA, with the most complete FAIR implementation, has a score of 3.51 out of 4.

Technical analysis of the front-end

For the purpose of identifying the reasons behind the low scores in the Copernicus hubs, we will extract the metadata tags, and do a comparative analysis between the Marine hub and the PANGAEA one.

Copernicus Marine

@prefix ns2: <http://ogp.me/ns#> .

ns2:description "The Black Sea (BS) Physical Reanalysis system (version E3R1) provides monthly and daily ocean fields for the Black Sea basin starting from 01/01/1992. These fields are temporal averages of 3D variables like temperature, salinity, zonal and meridional velocity components and 2D variables such as mixed layer depth, bottom temperature and sea surface height. The hydrodynamical core is based on NEMO general circulation ocean model (version 3.6; Madec et al., 2016), implemented in the BS domain with horizontal resolution of 1/27° x 1/36° and 31 vertical levels." ;

ns2:image

"https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/IMG/BLKSEA_MULTIIYEAR_PHY_007_004.png"

;

ns2:title "Black Sea Physics Reanalysis" ;

ns2:type "website" .

PANGAEA

@prefix ns1: <<http://www.w3.org/2007/05/powder-s#>> .

@prefix ns3: <<http://ogp.me/ns#>> .

@prefix sc: <<http://schema.org/>> .

sc:abstract ""We present station-specific depth integrated abundance and biomass of Calanus spp. [...]" ;

sc:datePublished "2020-04-02";

sc:description "We present station-specific depth integrated abundance and biomass of Calanus spp.[...]" ;

sc:datePublished "2019";

sc:Date ;

sc:identifier

"https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbz044" ;

sc:isPartOf [a sc:CreativeWorkSeries ;
sc:name "Journal of Plankton Research"

],

[a sc:CreativeWorkSeries ;
sc:name "Journal of Plankton Research"]

;

sc:issueNumber "41(5)" ;

sc:name "North Atlantic right whale (Eubalaena glacialis) and its food: (II) interannual variations in biomass of Calanus spp. on western North Atlantic shelves" ;

sc:pagination "687-708" ;

sc:url <<https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbz044>> .

sc:Person ;

sc:familyName "Johnson" ;

sc:givenName "Catherine" ;

sc:identifier "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5291-3141" ;

sc:name "Catherine Johnson" .

From a technical point, it is evident that the appropriate meta tags are missing from the Copernicus HTML code, what needs to be established is if the actual information that would map to the missing tags is present, or missing entirely. If it is present, the process to make this specific resource FAIR compliant would be simplified.

DOI (product):

https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004

Product Citation: Please refer to our Technical FAQ for citing products.<http://marine.copernicus.eu/faq/cite-cmems-products-cmems-credit?ldpage=169>

References:

- Lima, L., Aydogdu, A., Escudier, R., Masina, S., Ciliberti, S. A., Azevedo, D., Peneva, E. L., Causio, S., Cipollone, A., Clementi, E., Cretí, S., Stefanizzi, L., Lecci, R., Palermo, F., Coppini, G., Pinardi, N., & Palazov, A. (2020). Black Sea Physical Reanalysis (CMEMS BS-Currents) (Version 1) Data set. Copernicus Monitoring Environment Marine Service (CMEMS). https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004

[Read less](#)

Classification

Full name	Black Sea Physics Reanalysis
Product ID	BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004
DOI	10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Black Sea · Lat 40.86° to 46.8° · Lon 27.32° to 41.96°
Spatial resolution	0.037° × 0.028°
Temporal extent	Since 1 Jan 1993
Temporal resolution	Daily · Monthly
Elevation (depth) levels	31
Processing level	Level 4
Variables	Cell thickness · Eastward sea water velocity (UV) · Model level number at sea floor · Northward sea water velocity (UV) · Ocean mixed layer thickness (MLD) · Sea floor depth below geoid · Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) · Sea surface height above sea level (SSH) · Sea water potential temperature (T) · Sea water potential temperature at sea floor (bottomT) · Sea water salinity (S)
Feature type	Grid
Blue markets	Policy & governance · Science & innovation · Extremes, hazards & safety · Coastal services · Natural resources & energy · Trade & marine navigation
Projection	WGS 84 (EPSG 4326)
Data assimilation	Sea Level · In-Situ TS Profiles
Update frequency	Monthly · Biannually
Format	NetCDF-4
Last metadata update	14 October 2016
Originating centre	ULiège (Belgium)

Looking at the information present on the page, we can see that it has a DOI, which fits the persistent ID subprinciple from F, but it is not defined properly using, for example, the DC.identifier metatag from Dublin Core schemas (or any other schema). The implementation of it would look like this `<meta name="DC.identifier" content="https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004" scheme="DCTERMS.URI">`. Other information related to FAIR metatags is present in text form, meaning it has to be also available in a format that would facilitate FAIR compliance. Digging further through the HTML source, the following JS injected snippet is found:

```

{
  "props": {
    "pageProps": {
      "dataPackage": {
        "dataset": {
          "id": "BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004",
          "altId": "03e6da65-817c-48c7-9d79-ac5d33bab289",
          "title": "Black Sea Physics Reanalysis",
          "creationDate": "2016-10-14",
          "modifiedDate": "2016-10-14",
          "abstract": "The Black Sea (BS) Physical Reanalysis [...]",
          "doi": "10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004",
          "thumbnailUrl": "https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/IMG/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004.png",
          "contacts": [
            {
              "name": "Atanas Palazov",
            }
          ],
          "updateFrequencies": {},
          "keywords": {
            "oceanographic-geographical-features": "theme",
          },
          "assimilatedData": ["In-Situ TS Profiles"],
          "formats": [
            "NetCDF-4"
          ],
          "tempExtentBegin": "1993-01-01",
          "geoExtent": {
            "coordinates": []
          },
          "areas": ["Black Sea"],
          "sources": ["Numerical models"],
          "originatingCenter": "Uliège (Belgium)",
          "communities": ["Policy & governance"],
          "processingLevel": "Level 4",
          "allVariables": ["Cell thickness"],
          "mainVariables": [
            "Mixed layer thickness",
            "Salinity",
            "Sea surface height",
            "Temperature",
            "Velocity"
          ]
        },
      },
    },
  },
}

```

This snippet shows that sufficient information is present on the page to raise the F, A, and R scores for this particular Copernicus hub. Only fully missing information that would satisfy the Interoperability principle's standardised vocabulary/ontology guidelines.

The below table presents the core, or domain agnostic, metatags that should be at minimum implemented/mapped to the available information on the Copernicus hub.

Table 1. Core metadata

Metadata	Dublin Core	Schema.org	Data Cite
Identifier	dcterms:identifier	schema:identifier	datacite:identifier
Title	dcterms:title	schema:name	datacite:title
Creator	dcterms:creator	schema:author	datacite:creator
Publisher	dcterms:publisher	schema:publisher	datacite:publisher
Pub Date	dcterms:date	schema:datePublished	datacite:publicationYear
Abstract	dcterms:abstract	schema:abstract	datacite:abstract
Description	dcterms:description	schema:description	datacite:description

<i>Keywords</i>	dcterms:subject	schema:keywords	datacite:subject
<i>License</i>	dcterms:license	schema:license	datacite:rights
<i>Type</i>	dcterms:type	schema:type	datacite:resourceTypeGeneral
<i>Version</i>	N/A	schema:version	datacite:version
<i>Access Rights</i>	dcterms:accessRights	schema:conditionsOfAccess	N/A

Technical analysis of the back-end/databases

While the previous section focused on the FAIRness as assessed through the services' web interfaces, this section tackles the back-end/database part of said services.

In the most basic sense, the back-end is what answers the requests made by users through the web interface (generally called a front-end) or through APIs., by itself it cannot be accessed directly by users. Back-end complexity increases with functionality, and functionality is dependent on how specific or broad a platform/service is. Copernicus' back-end is a behemoth that is responsible for a number of essential operations, without which users would not be able to request data. It handles data ingestion from various data providers, as well as the processing, computing, and transforming of it in a format that the service can serve to users. This is where the final steps for standardisation can happen.

Standardisation is a crucial aspect of ensuring that data and related resources are organised and described in a consistent and machine-readable manner.

Efforts towards standardisation in databases will involve several facets, including the data structure, metadata, and terminology used to describe the data. Employing a common data model, like RDF, will facilitate the sharing and integration of data across various databases and systems. Similarly, using common metadata standards such as Dublin Core or Schema.org can enhance the discovery and reuse of data.

Standardisation plays a critical role in the interfaces and protocols used to access and manipulate the data. Adopting common APIs or data exchange formats like JSON or XML can facilitate interoperability between different systems. In addition, products and services linked to databases can benefit from the use of such standardised interfaces and protocols.

It is worth noting that standardisation also makes it easier to compare and evaluate different products and services. Common metrics and benchmarks can enhance the assessment of their performance and capabilities. This is especially pertinent in publicly funded scientific research, where the accuracy and reliability of data are of utmost importance.

Standardisation is a fundamental aspect of promoting the FAIR principles of data management in databases and the products/services linked to them. By standardising data structures, metadata, interfaces, protocols, data sharing, and integration can be enhanced, eventually leading to complex and powerful systems that can access and manipulate data from multiple sources.

However, as the backend databases of these services are inherently private, we can only assume how FAIR they are based on the data outputted to the web interface. This approach is limited; as it's possible the database does indeed contain the required information in the necessary format to tick all the FAIRness boxes, yet are simply not exposed on the interface. Adding to this limitation, is the fact that these services rely on external organisations to act as data providers, with each organisation having different internal workflows, which could not aid with the FAIRification and standardisation. A general discussion on how FAIR needs to be implemented, at organisational level will follow this section.

5.4 FAIR technical implementation discussion

With the current FAIR guidelines, there is no specific/concrete way of handling the technical implementation of the principles, thus the choice of “how” falls on the stakeholders, which is a challenging task that presents several hurdles that need to be overcome.

One of the main hurdles is the lack of standardization in data management practices. Different research fields, institutions, and organizations may have different ways of collecting, organizing, and sharing data, making it difficult to implement common data formats, models, and metadata standards.

Another hurdle is related to funding and politics, as implementing the FAIR principles requires significant investments in IT infrastructure, data curation and annotation, and personnel training. Many institutions and organizations may not have the necessary resources to invest in these areas, which can make it difficult to implement the FAIR principles. In the cases where the resources are present, data privacy and security concerns may also become an issue as the data may contain sensitive information that should not be shared publicly, even as metadata.

Culture, or rather the status quo, will likely be another important hurdle because the FAIR principles require a shift in how research is conducted, how data is managed, shared and reused. Researchers may be resistant to change, may not be familiar with best practices in data management, and may simply not be motivated to invest time and resources in data management if the benefits are too abstract or not immediate enough.

Overall, implementing the FAIR principles in scientific data management, especially under their current form, requires a significant effort and resources, and overcoming these hurdles requires collaboration and commitment from researchers, institutions, and organizations. Until the guidelines morph into a standard, or develop into a more concrete form, the following sections will tackle some generic technical points.

Metadata embedding / serving

Metadata to richly describe resources can be served or embedded through various methods.

One of the more popular methods being HTML [microdata](#) and HTML [meta tags](#), through the `itemscope/itemprop/itemtype` attributes. This *generally* allows search engines to crawl the

resources and report them richly in the search engine results page, allowing both humans and machines to faster locate relevant data.

Another method that is becoming more popular, having Google's backing, is through [JSON-LD](#), which essentially embeds in the HTML page source a JSON derived snippet, references it through a HTML `<link>` element, or through a HTTP Link header response.

```
# HTML Embed
<script type="application/ld+json">
  {
    "@context": "https://schema.org/",
    "@type": "Person",
    "name": "John Doe"
  }
</script>
# HTML Link element
<link rel="describedby" href="https://example.com/hello.jsonld" type="application/ld+json" >

# HTTP Header
Link: <https://example.com/hello.jsonld>; rel="alternate";
type="application/ld+json"
```

The preferred method, for search engine optimization, is the HTML embedding. A benefit of using JSON-LD over microdata/meta tags, is that in theory it is easier to implement as it allows decoupling the template engine (front-end) from the metadata provider (back-end). With microdata, the templates served by the template engine would need to be manually changed/updated, in addition to whatever changes the back-end might require. With JSON-LD embedding, this could be done programmatically just from the backend by linking the metadata provider to a model, then injecting it on page serve.

Historically, there exists a tendency of reinventing the wheel, either through the creation of new protocols that only serve a specific niche – only to be abandoned long-term – or through creating various frameworks/libraries that do not gain sufficient traction to be maintained. As the spirit of FAIR is about sustainability and reusability, specifically long-term, any such instinct of wheel discombobulation should be smothered.

Schemas / Vocabs / Ontologies

As mentioned before, implementing FAIR depends on domain agnostic schemas and domain specific schemas. For domain agnostic ones, in general a good rule of thumb is to use one that is already heavily used / very well supported. Google supports both Dublin Core and Schema.org, but Schema.org is favoured specifically for [Dataset Search](#), so for enhancing findability, it would be a good idea to use it when describing the metadata presented in Table 1.

6. Domain specific mapping

Domain agnostic metatags are the bare minimum to make a resource be on the path of FAIRness, however, they alone are not sufficient to richly describe all the possible data types. The solution is given by domain specific schemas, vocabs, and ontologies, developed by the scientific communities they must serve. [Bioschemas.org](https://bioschemas.org) and [Science-on-Schema.org](https://science-on-schema.org) are examples of schema.org specific communities.

Below we present a non-exhaustive list of mappings.

Metadata		Mandatory/Optional DANUBIUS proposal	Results WP11	DCAT - mapping	DCAT/OWL - definition
Research Infrastructure	General	RI Name	M-A	M	
		RI Abbreviation	M-A	M	
		URL to Data	M-A	M	
		URL to Research Infrastructure	O-A	M	
Supersite, Node, etc.	General	Name	M-A	M	dct:publisher publisher dct:publisher foaf:Agent This property refers to an entity (organisation) responsible for making the Catalogue available. 1..1
		Abbreviation/Identifier	O-A	M	
		Abstract/description	M-A	M	dct:description description dct:description rdfs:Literal This property contains a free-text account of the Catalogue. This property can be repeated for parallel language versions of the description. For further information on multilingual issues, please refer to section 8. 1..n
		Status (operational, closed, etc)	M-A	M	
		Country	M-A	M	dct:spatial spatial/ geographic dct:spatial dct:Location This property refers to a geographical area covered by the Catalogue. 0..n
		Continent	O-A	M	
		Operational start date	M-A	M	dcat:startDate start date dcat:startDate rdfs:Literal typed as xsd:date or xsd:dateTime This property contains the start of the period 0..1
		Operational end date	O-A	M	dcat:endDate end date dcat:endDate rdfs:Literal typed as xsd:date or xsd:dateTime This property contains the end of the period 0..1
		Type (campaign, project, meteo, ...)	M-A	M	skos:Concept Publisher type A type of organisation that acts as a publisher skos:Concept http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-adms/#dcterms-type
		Citation/Reference	O-A	M	

		URL to Data	O-A	M		
		URL to Supersite/Node	O-A	M		
		Acknowledgement	O-A	M		
		EPSG Code to identify the Coordinate Reference System	O-A	M		
	Contact point	Full name	M-A	M	dcat:contactPoint	dcat:contactPoint Recommendedproperty (Dataset) Updated Updates URI: adms:contactPoint→dcat:contactPoint Range: VCard→vCard:Kind MO8 1.1
		Position/task	M-A	M	vcard:Kind	contact point dcat:contactPoint vcard:Kind This property contains contact information that can be used for sending comments about the Dataset. 0..n
		Phone	O-A	M		
		E-mail	M-A	M	vcard:Kind	contact point dcat:contactPoint vcard:Kind This property contains contact information that can be used for sending comments about the Dataset. 0..n
		Address	O-A	M		
		Organistaion(s) name	M-A	M	foaf:Agent	publisher dct:publisher foaf:Agent This property refers to an entity (organisation) responsible for making the Dataset available. 0..1
		Organisation(s) abbreviation	O-A	M		
		Role/task of organisation(s) (data measuring, data preparation, ...)	O-A	M		
		ID (URL - ORCID, ..)	O-A	M		
Research Site <i>(is an institution/organisation at a given Supersite/Nole location which includes one</i>	General	Site ID	M-A	M		
		Site Name	M-A	M	dct:Location	spatial/ geographical coverage dct:spatial dct:Location This property refers to a geographic region that is covered by the Dataset. 0..n

<i>or several stations/plots/laboratories corresponding to different gathered data and/or data results)</i>	Contact person(s)	Location	M-A	M	dct:Location	spatial/ geographical coverage dct:spatial dct:Location This property refers to a geographic region that is covered by the Dataset. 0..n
		General Description	O-A	M		
		Full Name	O-A	M		
		email		O		
		Address		O		
	Metadata information	Creation date and time of the record	O-A	M	dct:temporal	temporal coverage dct:temporal dct:PeriodOfTime This property refers to a temporal period that the Dataset covers. 0..n
		Update date of the record	O-A	M		
		Metadata creator	O-A	M	dct:creator	dcat:contactPoint Recommendedproperty (Dataset) Updated Updates URI: adms:contactPoint→dcat:contactPoint Range: VCard→vCard:Kind MO8 1.1
	Research focus	Availability of contextual variables (if yes fill ContextData page)	O-A	M		
		Climate class	O-A	M		
Station/Plot/Trial/Laboratory/Sensor/Facility (data sources instruments/sensors/station/etc.)	General	Name	M-A	M	dct:title	Title dct:title rdfs:Literal This property contains a name given to the Catalogue. This property can be repeated for parallel language versions of the name. 1..n
		Abbreviation	O-A	M		
		Quality flag (checked, unchecked, etc)	O-A	M		
		Comments	O-A	M		
		Irrigated station (yes: year around/partially ; no)	O-N	M		

		Calibration of sensors (lab: yes/no; field: yes/no)	O-A	M			
	Location	Location (EPSG: 4326 WGS 84 / Lat/lon)	M-A	M	dct:Location	spatial/ geographical coverage dct:spatial dct:Location This property refers to a geographic region that is covered by the Dataset. 0..n	
		Location (original coordinate system)	O-A	M			
		Altitude (m asl)	O-A	M			
	properties	Land cover	M-A	M			
		Land use	O-N	M			
	Image/photo	Image name	O-A	M			
		Image description	O-A	M			
		Image file	O-A	M			
		Image creation date	O-A	M			
	Experimentation or observation focus	Experimental treatment ID	N-N	M			
		Treatment description: manipulated factors when there are experimental treatment	N-N	M			
	General Data Information	Dataset	Resource PID				
			Resource title				
Resource abstract							
Resource type							
Date							

		Data type				
		Language				
		Resource identifier				
		Topic				
		Keyword(s)				
		Character Encoding				
		Provenance	O-A	M		
		Acquisition time (UTC Shift)	M-A	M	dct:temporal	temporal coverage dct:temporal dct:PeriodOfTime This property refers to a temporal period that the Dataset covers. 0..n
		Quality flag (CEOS flags or own definition)	O-A	M		
		Measured/Interpolated Flag	O-A	M		
		Data processing (filtering, calibration, gap filling, measurement aggregation (in space (replication), in time))	M-A	M	dct:ProvenanceStatement	provenance dct:provenance dct:ProvenanceStatement This property contains a statement about the lineage of a Dataset. 0..n
		Availability	O-A	M	dct:accessRights	dct:accessRights Optional property (Data Service) New Range : dct:RightsStatement This property MAY include information regarding access or restrictions based on privacy, security, or other policies. DCAT-AP-73 2.0
		Accessibility (External Acces to data from the web)	O-A	M	dcat:accessURL	access URL dcat:accessURL rdfs:Resource This property contains a URL that gives access to a Distribution of the Dataset. The resource at the access URL may contain information about how to get the Dataset. 1..n
		Ownership	O-A	M		

		Storage format (ascii File, excel file, netcdf, relational DB, ...)	O-A	M		
	Rights and license information	Access Rights / Restrictions				
		License name				
		License url				
	Resource creator	Responsible organisation				
		Authors	O-A	M	dct:creator	dcat:contactPoint Recommendedproperty (Dataset) Updated Updates URI: adms:contactPoint→dcat:contactPoint Range: VCard→vCard:Kind MO8 1.1
		AuthorContact				
		Contributor				
		ContributorContact				
		URL				
	Resource contact	Name				
		Organisation name				
		Individual contact				
		Role/Position				
	Bibliographic Citation	Citation/Reference				

7. References

Copernicus Climate (2021) *The Climate Data Store / Copernicus*. 2021. <https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-data-store> [Accessed: 7 December 2022].

Devaraju, A., Huber, R., Mokrane, M., Herterich, P., Cepinskas, L., de Vries, J., L'Hours, H., Davidson, J. & White, A. (2022) *FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics*. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6461229.

FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (2020) *FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines*. doi:10.15497/rda00050.

Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R.R., Edmunds, R., et al. (2020) The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data*. 7 (1), 144. doi:10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7.

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., et al. (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*. 3 (1), 160018. doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

8. Annex

The screenshot displays a web interface for evaluating a resource. At the top, the URL <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331> is shown. Below it, the identifier of the evaluation is <https://w3id.org/fair-enough/evaluations/3a905bf0eed4c8fa6329b3921318f793a8d87179>, and it was evaluated in 4s with the `fair-enough-metadata` collection on 2022-11-13.

The extracted metadata section shows the license: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

The evaluation score is 12/16, represented by a circular progress indicator at 75%. A dropdown menu for 'Log level' is set to 'Success, warnings and failures'.

The 'Findable' section lists the following metrics:

- F1 - Resource identifier is persistent** (Failure):
https://w3id.org/fair-enough/metrics/tests/f1-metadata-identifier-persistent - Version: 0.7.0 - Metric to test if the unique identifier of the metadata resource is likely to be persistent. We test known URL persistence schemas (purl, doi, w3id, identifiers.org).
Test result URL: <https://w3id.org/fair-enough/metrics/metrics/f1-metadata-identifier-persistent#https%3A%2F%2Fdoi.pangaea.de%2F10.1594%2FPANGAEA.914331%2Fresult-2022-06-29T12:33:59+01:00>
FAILURE: [2022-11-13T14:05:48] The given resource URI <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331> is not considered a persistent URL
- F1 - Resource metadata identifier is unique** (Success)
- F3 - Metadata is grounded and machine-readable** (Success)

List of metrics with details and results

[Export](#)

Principle	Name	Description	Comment	Recommendation	Score	Result	Test	Details
F1A	Unique IDs				2	Success	Check	+
F1B	Persistent IDs				2	Success	Check	+
F2A	Structured metadata				2	Success	Check	+
F2B	Shared vocabularies for metadata			You should express all your metadata with properties Read more	1	Success	Check	+
A1.1	Open resolution protocol				2	Success	Check	+
I1	Machine readable format				2	Success	Check	+
I2	Use shared ontologies			You should express all your metadata with properties Read more	1	Success	Check	+
I3	External links				2	Success	Check	+
R1.1	Metadata includes license				2	Success	Check	+
R1.2	Metadata includes provenance			You should include information about provenance in your Read more	0	Failure	Check	+
R1.3	Community standards			You should express all your metadata with properties Read more	1	Success	Check	+

For additional tips and recommendations on how to improve your resource, we recommend you to use the FAIR Cookbook:
<https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/home.html>

Check

How FAIR is my resource ?

Enter resource identifier (URL/DOI)

✓ Test all metrics

The URL/DOI is valid - The input contains the following DOIs that you can also test: [10.1594/PANGAEA.914331](#)

Clean results

- [Dataset Dataverse](#)
- [Workflow](#)
- [Publication Datacite](#)
- [Dataset](#)
- [Tool](#)

Radar chart of metrics completion

Findable

- ❗ F1 - Resource identifier is persistent
- ✔ F1 - Resource metadata identifier is unique
- ✔ F2 - Metadata is grounded and machine-readable
- ✔ F2 - Metadata is structured
- ❗ F3 - Metadata identifier explicitly in metadata
- ❗ F4 - The resource is indexed in a searchable resource

Accessible

- ✔ A1.1 - Metadata uses an open free protocol for metadata retrieval
- ✔ A1.2 - Metadata authentication and authorization
- ❗ A2 - Metadata is persistent

Interoperable

- ✔ I1 - Metadata uses a formal semantic knowledge representation language
- ✔ I1 - Metadata uses a formal structured knowledge representation language
- ✔ I2 - Metadata uses FAIR Vocabularies registered in known repositories
- ✔ I2 - Metadata uses resolvable FAIR Vocabularies
- ✔ I3 - Metadata contains outward references

Reusable

- ✔ R1 - Metadata includes a License
- ✔ R1 - Metadata includes a standard License

FAIR assessment

Disclaimer:

The test results shown here are based on preliminary data and code which still is under development. F-UJI is rapidly evolving and not yet available in a productive environment.

[Click here to assess another data set](#)

Assessment Results:

Evaluated Resource:

Abundance and biomass of Calanus spp. and near surface and bottom temperature and salinity on western North Atlantic Shelves

[Save](#) [JSON](#) [New](#)

FAIR level: ?

advanced

Resource PID/URL: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.914331>

DataCite support: enabled

Metric Version: metrics_v0.5

Metric Specification: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>

Software version: 2.2.1

Download assessment results: [JSON](#)

Save and share assessment results:

Summary:

	Score earned:		Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	advanced
Accessible:	3 of 3	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	advanced
Interoperable:	4 of 4	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	advanced
Reusable:	7 of 10	<input type="radio"/>	moderate

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✓	∨
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✓	∨
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✓	∨
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✓	∨
FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved programmatically.	✓	∨

Accessible

FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	✓	∨
FsF-A1-03D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	✓	∨
FsF-A1-02M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	✓	∨

Interoperable

FsF-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	✓	∨
FsF-I2-01M - Metadata uses semantic resources	✓	∨
FsF-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	✓	∨

Reusable

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.	✓	∨
FsF-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	✓	∨
FsF-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	✓	∨
FsF-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.	✓	∨
FsF-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.	✓	∨

DOI (product):

https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004

Product Citation: Please refer to our Technical FAQ for citing products.<http://marine.copernicus.eu/faq/cite-cmems-products-cmems-credit/?idpage=169>

References:

- Lima, L., Aydogdu, A., Escudier, R., Masina, S., Ciliberti, S. A., Azevedo, D., Peneva, E. L., Causio, S., Cipollone, A., Clementi, E., Cretí, S., Stefanizzi, L., Lecci, R., Palermo, F., Coppini, G., Pinardi, N., & Palazov, A. (2020). Black Sea Physical Reanalysis (CMEMS BS-Currents) (Version 1) Data set. Copernicus Monitoring Environment Marine Service (CMEMS). https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004

[Read less](#)

Classification

Full name	Black Sea Physics Reanalysis
Product ID	BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004
DOI	10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004
Source	Numerical models
Spatial extent	Black Sea · Lat 40.86° to 46.8° · Lon 27.32° to 41.96°
Spatial resolution	0.037° × 0.028°
Temporal extent	Since 1 Jan 1993
Temporal resolution	Daily · Monthly
Elevation (depth) levels	31
Processing level	Level 4
Variables	Cell thickness · Eastward sea water velocity (UV) · Model level number at sea floor · Northward sea water velocity (UV) · Ocean mixed layer thickness (MLD) · Sea floor depth below geoid · Sea surface height above geoid (SSH) · Sea surface height above sea level (SSH) · Sea water potential temperature (T) · Sea water potential temperature at sea floor (bottomT) · Sea water salinity (S)
Feature type	Grid
Blue markets	Policy & governance · Science & innovation · Extremes, hazards & safety · Coastal services · Natural resources & energy · Trade & marine navigation
Projection	WGS 84 (EPSG 4326)
Data assimilation	Sea Level · In-Situ TS Profiles
Update frequency	Monthly · Biannually
Format	NetCDF-4
Last metadata update	14 October 2016
Originating centre	ULiège (Belgium)